

Life by Year
One Googol

Can you imagine how life will be?

Googol is 1 followed by 100 zeros.

It's a very large number but have you ever wondered how life will be in that particular year?

Can you imagine?

?

© *Copyright*

Albi Ndoni
Tirana, Albania
01/29/2024